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Effect of Peer Tutoring Strategy on Upper Basic II Students' Interest in Basic Science and Technology in Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of peer tutoring strategy on Upper Basic II students' interest in Basic Science and Technology in Otukpo Local Government Area (LGA), Benue State, Nigeria. Two research questions were asked and answered, and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Simple random sampling techniques were used to sample 85 (44 Male and 41 Female) students in two intact classes from the population of 4,834 Upper Basic II students. Basic Science and Technology Interest Scale (BSTIS) was used for data collection. A reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha formula. Data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation, to answer research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Findings of the study showed that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring instructional strategy and those taught with lecture methods, among others. Based on the findings, it was concluded

that appropriate use of peer tutoring instructional strategy in teaching Basic Science and Technology would facilitate students' interest in Basic Science and Technology, in Otukpo LGA. Therefore, it was recommended that Basic Science and Technology teachers should be encouraged to adopt peer tutoring instructional strategy in teaching Basic Science and Technology as it increases both male and female students' interest in the subject.

Keywords: Peer Tutoring, Interest, Basic Science and Technology, Upper Basic II Students, Science Education, Teaching Methods

Introduction

Education remains a critical tool for national development, and at the heart of educational achievement is the academic performance of students. In Nigeria, the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme emphasizes the importance of quality education at the basic level, including the teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology (BST), a core subject that introduces learners to scientific inquiry, innovation, and technological advancement. BST is a subject that demands practical engagement, critical thinking, and curiosity, the impact of peer influence becomes particularly significant. Students who associate with academically driven peers are more likely to develop interest and competence in BST, while those who align with unserious or anti-school groups may develop negative attitudes towards science learning. However, numerous factors affect students' interest and academic achievement in BST, among which peer group pressure stands out, particularly at the Upper Basic II level, a developmental stage characterized by a strong desire for social acceptance.

The importance of BST has been seen in different aspects of society. Adegoke (2015) noted that by introducing Basic science curriculum to students in secondary schools, society and the students could benefit in several ways namely: reducing poverty in the society; developing creative skills for the students; improving the health status of the students and those around them; improving the living conditions of their parents in the long run; and empowering students to convert natural physical objects in their environment for wealth creation. On another note, Agbidye (2015) stated that Basic science functions as the basis upon which some required training in scientific skills is provided in order to meet the growing needs of the society and attain good academic achievement and high interest in science.

Interest has been found to be a very powerful motivational process that energizes learning and is essential to academic success. Ezike in Yusuf (2011), defined interest as the feeling of concern or curiosity about an object. Interest of a student in any subject is an energizer for a meaningful learning to take place (Abakpa, 2011). Interest is seen as that quality which arouses curiosity, and as such holds a student's attention to a learning activity. When a student develops interest in a particular subject, the student will definitely derive satisfaction from the knowledge of the subject as he/she studies the said subject. Ebute and Aende (2024) states that interest could also be developed as students interact with peers. Students develop confidence and knowledge on peer tutoring. It encourages communal learning, cooperative learning and peer collaboration with one another. Studies have shown that it is superior to group instruction since it addresses special needs, learner pace, style and

level of understanding. This apparently gives social and emotional gains which helps to increase interest. In this study, students' interest in Basic Science and Technology is considered as the state of showing concern, curiosity and preference for the subject. Aremu and Sokan in Nwankwo and Okolie (2019), argue that interest and academic achievement is not only determined by intellectual capacity but also by social and emotional support systems such as family background, teacher influence, and peer associations as well as gender.

Gender is a category of sex, either male or female into which sexually reproducing organisms are divided on the basis of their reproductive roles in their species. Gender imbalance is conceived as the structural relationship of inequality between males and females as manifested in education. Gender inequality in education has remained a perennial problem of global scope (UNESCO, 2021). Jirgba *et.al.* (2018) stated that in Nigeria, as in other countries of the world, Science and Technology are usually viewed as male dominant subjects. Girls opt for careers in humanities and social science related careers. Gender differences in science interest and achievement have been a major concern and science educators seek to provide avenues for achieving gender equity for sustainable development. The performance in the science at both upper basic and senior secondary school levels of education vary across genders. It appears that female students are more interested in the non-science subjects more than the science subjects in which basic science and technology is inclusive at the upper basic education levels and senior secondary school classes (Okeke in Jirgba *et.al.* 2019). Fadare *et. al.* (2021) states that peer group tutoring also influences the development of children's socializing skills. They learn from a peer how to cooperate and socialize according to group norms and group-sanctioned modes of behaviour. Wael in Tartenger *et. al.*, (2024) suggested the used of peer-tutoring strategy.

Peer-tutoring strategy is a cooperative teaching and learning procedure that requires active participation of the learners. It is an instructional strategy where students help one another learn academic content, typically with one student acting as the tutor and the other as the learner. This approach encourages cooperative learning by allowing students to take an active role in teaching and learning processes. According to Tran in Tartenger *et. al.* (2024) peer-tutoring method does not only increase the performance of students but also promotes their communication abilities and interpersonal relationships. Usually, shy children learn effectively through tutoring by sharing their thoughts with classmates (Bombardelli, 2016). Peer-tutoring is an active teaching methodology that fosters student inclusion while enabling students to learn from each other (Cockerill, Craig & Thurston, 2018). Research has shown that peer tutoring improves learning outcomes and fosters positive attitudes towards science subjects. Ovie (2022) stated that peer tutoring significantly improves students' performance and learning attitudes. Also, Azeez *et. al.* (2022) found that peer-tutoring instructional strategies have significant effect on students' interest and academic achievement. Akinbobola and Afolabi (2010) indicated that students taught through peer tutoring performed significantly better in science subjects compared to those taught using conventional methods. Jegede and Adebayo (2013) emphasized that peer-led instructional strategies help to simplify complex science concepts, thereby enhancing student comprehension and interest. Igbokwe (2015) emphasized that poor academic achievement in science subjects could be traced to environmental and social factors, including the influence of unmotivated or deviant peer groups.

Despite the growing advocacy for learner-centered approaches in science education, there remains a paucity of empirical studies specifically addressing how peer tutoring strategy effect Upper Basic II students' interest and achievement in Basic Science and Technology in Otukpo LGA, Benue State. This study, therefore, seeks to explore the effect of peer tutoring strategy on Upper Basic II students' interest in Basic Science and Technology in Otukpo LGA, Benue State, Nigeria

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of peer tutoring strategy on Upper Basic II students' interest in Basic Science and Technology in Otukpo LGA, Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. determine the difference in the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional lecture method.
- ii. determine the difference in the mean interest ratings of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked and answered by the study.

- i. What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional lecture method?
- ii. What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- i. There is no significance difference in the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional lecture method.
- ii. There is no significance difference in the mean interest ratings of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design of non-equivalent pre-test, post-test control group type. The study was carried out in Otukpo Local Government Area (LGA), Benue State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 4,834 Upper Basic II students in all Basic Education Schools in Otukpo LGA. The sample size for the study was 85 (44 male and 41 female) Upper Basic II (JSS 2) students in co-educational public schools. The sample was drawn from 2 intact classes using a simple random sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was Basic Science and Technology Interest Scale (BSTIS). The instrument consisted of 20 items constructed on a 4-point rating scale of strongly Agree (SA=4 points), Agree (A=3 points), Disagree (D=2 points) and strongly disagree (SD=1 point). The research instrument was validated by two experts. One from the Department of Science Education Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, and one

Basic Science and Technology teacher. Their inputs and Suggestions helped in improving the quality of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of BSTIS was determined using Cronbach Alpha formula on 20 students which were part of the population but not part of the sample for the study which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.77. The Data was collected with the help of two research assistants from the sampled schools. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, whereas Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Results are presented according to order of research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional lecture method?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Interest Ratings of Students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy and those taught with Conventional Lecture Method

Group	N	Pre-Interest		Post-Interest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Peer Tutoring Strategy	43	3.01	0.32	3.56	0.13	0.55
Lecture Method	42	3.05	0.29	3.12	0.25	0.07
Mean Difference		0.04		0.44		0.48
Total	85					

The results presented in Table 1 show that the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy was 3.01 for pretest and 3.56 for the post-test with corresponding standard deviation of 0.32 and 0.13 respectively. However, the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with lecture method was 3.05 for the pretest and 3.12 for the post-test, with standard deviation of 0.29 and 0.25 respectively. The mean gain for the peer tutoring strategy group was 0.55 while the lecture method group was 0.07. The group mean difference was 0.04 for pre-test and 0.44 for post-test while the mean gain was 0.48 in favor of the peer tutoring strategy group.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Interest Ratings of Male and Female Students taught Basic Science and Technology with Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	22	3.02	0.32	3.55	0.15	0.53
Female	21	3.02	0.31	3.57	0.09	0.55
Mean Difference		0.00		0.02		0.02
Total	43					

The results presented in Table 2 show that the mean interest ratings of male students taught Basic Science and Technology with Peer Tutoring instructional strategy was 3.02 for pre-test and 3.55 for the post-test with corresponding standard deviation of 0.32 and 0.15 respectively. However, the mean interest ratings of female students taught Basic Science and Technology with Peer Tutoring instructional strategy was 3.02 for the pre-test and 3.57 for the post-test, with standard deviation of 0.31 and 0.09 respectively. The mean gain for the male students was 0.53 while the mean gain for the female students was 0.55. The group mean difference was 0.00 for pre-test and 0.02 for post-test while the mean gain was 0.02 in favour of the female students.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significance difference in the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy and those taught with conventional lecture method.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance of Interest Rating Scores of Students taught Basic Science and Technology with Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy and those taught using Lecture Method

Source	Type Sum of Squares	III of	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	4.345 ^a		2	2.172	59.963	.000	.594
Intercept	6.592		1	6.592	181.961	.000	.689
Pretest	.226		1	.226	6.242	.014	.071
Group	4.174		1	4.174	115.211	.000	.584
Error	2.971		82	.036			
Total	955.876		85				
Corrected Total	7.316		84				

a. R Squared = .594 (Adjusted R Squared = .584)

The result of the Analysis of Covariance presented in Table 3 shows that the P-value of 0.000 is less than .05 ($P < 0.05$) level of significance. This shows that the test was significant. The result implies that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significance difference was rejected. This means that students who were exposed to peer tutoring instructional strategy have more interest than those not exposed to peer tutoring instructional strategy.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significance difference in the mean interest ratings of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring strategy.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance of Interest Rating Scores of Male and Female Students taught Basic Science and Technology with Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy

RH3. Source	Type Sum of Squares	III df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	.008 ^a	2	.004	.243	.785	.012
Intercept	5.393	1	5.393	342.296	.000	.895
Pretest	.000	1	.000	.027	.871	.001
Gender	.007	1	.007	.460	.502	.011
Error	.630	40	.016			
Total	545.033	43				
Corrected Total	.638	42				

a. R Squared = .012 (Adjusted R Squared = -.037)

The result of the Analysis of Covariance presented in Table 4 shows that the p-value of 0.502 is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$) level of significance. This shows that the test was not significant. The result implies that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using the peer tutoring instructional strategy. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This means that peer tutoring instructional strategy increase the interest of both male and female students in Basic Science and Technology.

Discussion

The findings from research question one and hypothesis one revealed that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean interest ratings of students taught Basic Science and Technology with peer tutoring instructional strategy and those taught with lecture method. This finding was expected because of the students' active participation in the teaching and learning process. The findings of this study are supported by the findings of Ogunsola (2016), who found that students taught using peer tutoring exhibited higher

interest in the Technical Drawing, than those taught using lecture method. Also, the findings of the study agree with the findings of Abdulmalik and Torpev (2016) who found that slow learners taught by peer tutors using class-wide peer tutoring performed better and showed increased interest in Chemistry redox reaction than those taught using lecture method. Again, this finding is supported by the findings of Okeke *et.al.* (2024), who found that there was significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught Economics using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method in favour of the peer tutoring strategy. The finding is supported by the finding of Azeez *et al.* (2021), who found that peer tutoring can elevate student interest by witnessing their peers' success, thus fostering a supportive learning atmosphere. Moreover, the findings of the study agree with the findings of Ebute and Aende (2024), who found that there was a significant difference in the mean interest rating scores of students exposed to peer-tutoring strategy than those exposed to the conventional.

The findings in research question two and hypothesis two, revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean interest ratings of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using the peer tutoring instructional strategy. This finding is supported by the findings of Ebute and Aende (2024), who found that there was no significant difference in the mean interest rating scores of male and female students who are taught Social Studies with peer tutoring strategy. Moreover, the findings of the study agree with the findings of Okeke *et.al.* (2024), who found that there is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Economics using peer tutoring strategy. The findings of this study negate the finding of Oguegbu, *et. al.*, (2024) who found that a notable gender difference exists in the mean interest scores of male and female students who were instructed in mathematics via peer tutoring.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the findings, it was concluded that appropriate use of peer tutoring instructional strategy in teaching Basic Science and Technology would facilitate students' interest in Basic Science and Technology, in Otukpo LGA. The strategy is gender friendly as both male and female students developed high interest in Basic Science and Technology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Basic Science and Technology teachers should be encouraged to adopt peer tutoring instructional strategy in teaching Basic Science and Technology as it increases students' interest in the subject.
- ii. Peer tutoring instructional strategy is gender friendly and should therefore be used in teaching of Basic Science and Technology to enhance the interest of male and female students in the subject.

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